

THE LIVABILITY RANKING OF CITIES IN UZBEKISTAN FOR 2024

Muhammadjonov Azizbek Davoronjon o‘g‘li

Institute for Macroeconomics and Regional studies under Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan,
leading specialist of “Strategical planning of regional development” project

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17327607>

***Annotation.** This study develops a Livability Ranking for cities in Uzbekistan by adapting the Global Liveability Index methodology to national conditions. International indicators were replaced with locally available socio-economic and statistical measures. The results highlight that Tashkent, Bukhara, Urgench, Samarkand, and Navoi demonstrate higher livability compared to other cities, while smaller urban areas remain challenged in terms of infrastructure, healthcare, education, and public safety. The research underlines the need for improving regional statistics, enhancing survey practices, and integrating institutional data for comprehensive monitoring. Refining the index methodology in future stages will allow policymakers to identify problem areas, design targeted reforms, and ensure sustainable urban development across the country.*

***Keywords:** Livability Index, Global Liveability Index, urban development, Uzbekistan cities, socio-economic indicators, quality of life, infrastructure, healthcare, education, public safety, regional statistics, urban policy, sustainable development.*

Introduction.

Today, more than half of the world’s population – over 4 billion people – lives in cities. This shift is set to continue, with the urban population expected to more than double by 2050, at which point nearly 7 in 10 people will live in cities. Cities are engines of economic growth and development. They are the centers where most GDP is generated and most private sector jobs are created. As cities grow, they help entire regions and even countries to become more prosperous and productive. However, the rapid pace and scale of urbanization is also bringing significant challenges.¹ As cities expand, residents’ demand for improved infrastructure, public services, and a higher quality of life continues to grow. If urbanization is managed effectively, such demands can be adequately met. The ‘Uzbekistan-2030’ Strategy also places particular emphasis on this issue, outlining the implementation of an urbanization strategy across the regions of the republic, including the target of increasing the urbanization rate from 51 percent to 60 percent, as well as raising the number of cities with a population exceeding 300,000 to 28.² To watch how process going on, based on the 2024 socio-economic indicators of the country’s cities, a ‘Livability Ranking’ of Uzbek cities has been developed. In constructing this ranking, the methodology of the Global Liveability Index was employed. The Economist Intelligence Unit annually publishes the Global Liveability Ranking of cities worldwide. According to the 2023 results of this international index, Tashkent ranked 157th out of 173 cities. Based on the organization’s report, Uzbekistan’s capital received a score of 53.9, dropping 13 positions compared to the previous year and becoming one of the top ten cities with the most significant

¹ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/urbandevelopment/overview>

² <https://lex.uz/docs/-6600413>

decline in ranking.³ The core essence of the Livability Ranking of Uzbek Cities lies in assessing the conveniences created for city residents, the extent to which they feel safe and free, and their accessibility to available services such as education, healthcare, utilities, tourism, entertainment, and public services.

Methods.

Indicator Framework Applied in the Global Liveability Ranking

Subindex	Indicators within the Sub-Index	Source
Stability (25%)	Petty crime Violent crime Terrorism threat Armed conflicts Civil wars	EIU rating
Healthcare (20%)	Availability and quality of facilities in private healthcare institutions Availability and quality of facilities in public healthcare institutions Availability of over-the-counter medicines General healthcare indicators	EIU rating, World bank data
Culture and ecology (25%)	Humidity and average temperature indicators Unfavorable weather conditions as perceived by tourists Corruption indicator Social or religious restrictions Censorship indicator Availability of sports facilities Cultural indicators Food and beverages Consumer goods and services	EIU rating, Transparency International
Education (10%)	Private education opportunities Public education indicators	EIU rating, World bank data
Infrastructure (20%)	Quality of domestic roads Quality of public transport Availability of opportunities for international connectivity Indicator of access to quality housing Indicator of energy supply Indicator of access to clean drinking water Quality of telecommunications	EIU rating

Such indicators are maintained statistically for large cities such as Tashkent, but are not available for other cities of Uzbekistan. Taking this into account, the sub-indices and their respective weights applied in the Global Liveability methodology were retained, while the indicators used for calculation were substituted with those recorded in the national statistics. In the republic, a total of 32 cities have municipal governance structures, for which broader

³ The Global Liveability Index 2023 report

statistical data are available. The ranking covered cities with a population exceeding 40,000, while smaller cities such as G‘ozgon (9.2 thousand inhabitants) and Shirin (19.4 thousand inhabitants) were excluded. The Livability Ranking of Uzbek Cities was constructed using 27 quantitative and qualitative indicators. In calculating the composite index, most indicators were taken on a per capita basis in order to assess the individual accessibility of available opportunities and infrastructure. The Livability Index of Cities is determined based on the following formula:

$$LI = \sum_{i=1}^5 w_i x_i$$

Here, LI – denotes the Livability Index, w_i -represents the weight of the i sub-index, and x_i refers to the value of the i -sub-index. The sub-indices used in the calculation of the index are determined through the following expression:

$$x_i = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k y_{ij}$$

Here, k - denotes the number of indicators within the sub-index, and y_{ij} – i - represents the indicator of the j - sub-index.

Analysis and Results.

The analysis results indicate that the top five most livable cities in the republic are Tashkent (73.3 points on a 100-point scale), Bukhara (69.5), Urgench (64.6), Samarkand (63.1), and Navoi (61.4). At the bottom of the list, the five lowest-ranked cities are Kattaqo‘rg‘on (29.8), Bekobod (30.7), Yangiyer (32.9), Khanabad (32.9), and Nurafshan (33). Notably, according to the constructed ranking, all of the top ten most livable cities are regional centers. In addition, the non-regional urban settlements closest in ranking to this group were Kokand (15th place), Khiva (14th place), and Chirchik (21th place).

1.Socio-economic, stability.

In this category, the lowest indicators were recorded in Chirchik, Khanabad, Shahrisabz, and Nukus. In particular, the situation in Nukus is strongly influenced by population migration. The net migration rate relative to the city’s population is -1.7 per mille, ranking it second after Ohangaron (-1.9). This can be explained by population outflows to other regions due to geographic, climatic, and environmental conditions, as well as limited employment and income opportunities.

In Khanabad, the average wage is 1.2 times lower than in the regional center of Andijan and 1.7 times lower than in Tashkent, reflecting the scarcity of formal jobs. Similarly, in relatively developed cities such as Kokand, Margilan, Khiva, and Shahrisabz, the comparatively low level of average wages indicates a high proportion of the population engaged in informal economic activities.

2.Infrastructure.

In most cities, centralized drinking water and natural gas supply are relatively well-established. However, in the cities of Kashkadarya region, poor infrastructure indicators have negatively affected the rankings of Karshi and Shahrisabz. Specifically, Karshi ranks last among all cities in terms of drinking water supply, while Shahrisabz is 26th in centralized drinking water supply

and last in natural gas supply. Furthermore, significant disparities exist between cities in the number of retail and catering establishments. Urgench, Gulistan, Navoi, Tashkent, Bukhara, and Samarkand are leaders in this regard. The high level of disparity can be explained as follows: In Urgench, Gulistan, and Navoi, the number of such establishments per 10,000 inhabitants is relatively high because the populations of these regional centers are smaller compared to other centers (ranking 11th, 12th, and 13th by population size, respectively). Tashkent, Bukhara, and Samarkand, by contrast, are administrative and tourism hubs at the national level, which ensures the sufficient presence of retail and catering establishments.

3. Education.

There are no significant disparities among cities in terms of population coverage in general secondary and preschool education. However, other indicators such as quality of education (measured by university entrance exam scores), availability of secondary specialized education, and access to non-state secondary education are higher in leading cities. The largest number of private schools are concentrated in Tashkent (44), Fergana (14), Andijan (13), and Samarkand (8), with nearly 24,000 students enrolled (about two-thirds of all students in private general education schools). Currently, most of these schools are located in regional centers.

4. Healthcare.

There is a considerable gap between the top 10 cities in healthcare indicators and the remaining 20 cities. This indicates that access to healthcare services is much more convenient in regional centers compared to other cities. One reason is that specialized medical centers are located only in regional centers, creating significant disparities in the availability of healthcare staff and hospital beds. In addition, the influx of residents from surrounding regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan to regional centers and Tashkent increases demand for healthcare services, which in turn raises the overall share of services provided in these cities. Although Tashkent ranks first overall and hosts certain central medical institutions, it ranks only 12th in healthcare. This is explained by the discrepancy between the city's permanent population (around 3 million) and its actual resident and working population (around 5 million), which places a heavy burden on the capital's healthcare institutions.

5. Culture and environment.

Positive results were observed in Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, and the administrative center of Fergana region. These cities can also be recognized as the most attractive destinations for tourists in Uzbekistan. This is supported by their higher tourism indicators (capacity of hotels and recreation facilities, number of tour operators, and number of architectural monuments) as well as their more developed interregional transport infrastructure compared to other cities.

These cities are heavily industrialized, resulting in worse environmental conditions compared to other urban areas. For example, per capita emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere are particularly high in Almalyk (1275.6 kg), Nurafshon (463 kg), Ohangaron (206.4 kg), Angren (87.2 kg), Bekabad (47.9 kg), and Kuvasay (73.9 kg). By comparison, emissions in Almalyk are 95 times higher than in Bukhara, 59 times higher than in Urgench, and 37 times higher than in Samarkand.

Conclusion.

Introducing the livability rating into practice requires the active participation and cooperation of a wide range of ministries, agencies, and organizations. In this process, it is advisable to establish an integrated electronic platform that brings together all relevant databases

and ensures their timely updates. At the same time, developing effective mechanisms to strengthen the responsibility of institutions for maintaining and updating data on time is of key importance.

Currently, a number of indicators in Uzbekistan are collected at the national level, but are not systematically reported at the regional or city level. Compared to developed countries, the list of available regional indicators remains relatively limited, which restricts the scope of regional research. In addition, while many international organizations and national think tanks conduct surveys among the population on various topics, the accessibility and transparency of such survey results remain insufficient. Organizational challenges in attracting participants also create barriers to ensuring the periodicity and continuity of such surveys.

To improve the practical significance of the City Livability Index, it is recommended to expand its scope by including additional dimensions such as crime rates and road traffic accidents. Furthermore, at the next stages of development, the methodology will be enriched by incorporating public opinion surveys that reflect the views of different income groups, as well as expert assessments, thus making the index more comprehensive and reliable.

In conclusion, the practical application of this rating will make it possible to regularly monitor the overall situation in Uzbekistan's cities across several dimensions. Moreover, through continuous improvement of the methodology, problem areas in each direction can be identified, addressed, and the negative factors hindering sustainable economic development in the regions can be significantly reduced.

REFERENCES

1. The Economist Intelligence Unit (2024). Global Liveability Index 2024. Economist Group.
2. United Nations Human Settlements Programme (UN-Habitat) (2023). World Cities Report 2023: Envisioning the Future of Cities. Nairobi: UN-Habitat.
3. World Bank (2023). World Development Indicators. Washington, DC: World Bank.
4. State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics (2023–2024). Uzbekistan Statistical Yearbook. Tashkent.
5. Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2023). Socio-Economic Development Indicators of Regions. Tashkent.
6. Lex.uz Uzbekistan Strategy_2030